

Station: Manufacturing Working Conditions

Select your scenario!

from **A** (Working conditions good
 (few blocks))
 bis **D** (Working conditions bad
 (many blocks))

1x ≙ very good or good working conditions
2x ≙ satisfactory or sufficient working conditions
3x ≙ poor working conditions

Guiding questions:

The guiding questions help you gradually understand the differences between the scenarios and maintain an overview.

No blocks

A

B

C

D

I have my own smartphone or similar device [A].

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Fairphone / SHIFTphone.

iPhone / Samsung / Nothing.

Google Pixel / Huawei / Xiaomi.

My smartphone is ...

... received from relatives.

... purchased second-hand.

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... newly purchased.

My smartphone is ... years old

... > 3 years

... 3 years

... 1-2 years

... < 1 year

When the device is no longer needed, I will...

... pass it on.

... dispose it properly / recycle it.

... put it away.

... throw it away.